

Thermal Conductivity Measure of polymer with Flash Method.

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1. ABSTRACT

The polymers made by extrusion on production lines have mechanical properties that depend of many parameters: for example, the fiber rate, the cell rate, the resin rate. The thermal conductivity of materials depend also of these rate and that's why this measure can give information on the mechanics characteristics of the materials.

We show here, the flash method which is usually used to study the thermal diffusivity of homogeneous materials whose has high conductivity. In this paper, a study is presented on the application of this unsteady method to measure the thermal conductivity polymers which have a thermal conductivity about $1 \text{ W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$. We present here the experimental apparatus and the modelling of the transient heat transfer. Then, we illustrate a practical application: the evolution of the thermal conductivity of a plastic versus the fiber rate.

The measurements indicate that a relation exists between the conductivity and the rate of material in the plastic, these last phenomenon comes from the hazardous of fabrication process.

Keywords: Conductivity measure, Polymer, Flash method, thermal properties.

2. SYMBOLS FOR PHYSICAL QUANTITIES:

T	temperature :	K
θ	Laplace Transform of temperature	
Φ	heat flux :	W
ϕ	Laplace Transform of heat flux	
t	time :	s
p	complex variable :	s^{-1}
S	Sample area :	m^2
r	radial distance :	m
m	sample perimeter :	m
λ	heat conductivity :	$\text{W.m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$
$a=\lambda/\rho c$	thermal diffusivity :	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
ρ	density :	kg m^{-3}
c	specific heat :	$\text{J. kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
h	heat-transfer coefficient :	$\text{W.m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$
$R=e/\lambda.S$	Heat resistance:	K.W^{-1}
$C=\rho c e S$	heat capacity:	J.K^{-1}
*	dimensionless magnitude	
o,e	inlet ,outlet variables	

3. EXPERIMENT:

The measurements are made on a cylindrical sample of 2.5 centimetres in diameter. The material is sandwiched between two thin plates of same diameter. The thickness of the disks ranges from 0.1 mm to 2.5 mm, but we usually use 0.2 mm copper disk. For the jointing of sample within the disks, we use a thin layer of silicone grease or strong glue. The experimental device is composed of a flash and thermocouple in an insulating enclosure (see figure 1). The sample is horizontally held in position by three screws. It receive the heat pulse on its upper side which is covered with black paint. The energy of the pulse is distributed uniformly [1] onto the sample by a lot of beam reflections in the flash enclosure. The opposite metallic face gives the average temperature. The BiTe thermocouples are chosen for their good thermoelectric coefficient, the hot soldering is in contact with the metallic disk; the cold one is put in a block of copper which stays at room temperature. The transient temperature of the rear face of the sample is measured by a potentiometric recorder or by digital storage with a microcomputer. The pulse duration is about 10 ms. Such time is lower than measurement time, so we shall consider that the flash can be identified to a DIRAC function of time.

Figure 1 : Experimental apparatus.

4. THE MODELLING OF THE HEAT TRANSFER IN A MATERIAL: CLASSICAL FLASH METHOD

First we shall consider, the unidirectional heat transfer through a wall characterised by a thickness e , a thermal conductivity λ , a specific mass ρ , a specific heat c and a unit surface S (see figure 2).

Figure 2: Sample submitted to a Flash on its upper face and experimental thermogram.

The heat transfer is govern by the equations:

$$\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{a} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad \text{and} \quad -\lambda S \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right)_{x=0} = f(t) \quad (1)$$

If we uses the Laplace transform of T(t) and f(t) the equations become:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x^2} = \frac{p}{a} \theta \quad \text{and} \quad -\lambda S \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} \right)_{x=0} = \varphi \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \varphi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ \frac{-\lambda S p}{a} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \varphi \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The solution of the differential equation is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \varphi \end{bmatrix}_x = \begin{bmatrix} \text{ch}(\alpha x) & -\frac{\text{sh}(\alpha x)}{\lambda S} \\ -\lambda \alpha S \cdot \text{sh}(\alpha x) & \text{ch}(\alpha x) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \varphi \end{bmatrix}_{x=0} \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{p}{a}}$, ch et sh the hyperbolic cosine and sine.

The flux and the temperature are linked by the quadripolar equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta_0 \\ \varphi_0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & A \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_e \\ \varphi_e \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{where } A = \text{ch}(\chi); \quad B = \frac{e}{\lambda S} \text{sh}(\chi); \quad C = \frac{\lambda S}{e} \chi \text{ sh } \chi; \quad D = A \quad (5)$$

$$\text{with } \chi = \sqrt{\frac{pe^2}{a}}$$

As in electricity we have a quadripolar relation between the two vectors $\begin{bmatrix} \theta_0 \\ \varphi_0 \end{bmatrix}$ and $\begin{bmatrix} \theta_e \\ \varphi_e \end{bmatrix}$.

Parker model

In his model Parker consider that there were no heat loss on the sample faces and the heat flux was unidirectional. In these conditions, the flux φ_e which is equal to zero so we can write [2]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta_0 \\ \varphi_0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & A \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_e \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

This can be represented by the quadripole show on figure 3:

figure 3 : quadripole 1D

If we use a Flash on the upper face of the sample, which can be modeled by a DIRAC peak $\varphi(t) = q \cdot \delta(t)$ i.e. $\varphi(p) = q$. Thus

$$\theta_e = \frac{q}{C} = \frac{q}{\frac{\lambda}{e} \cdot \chi \cdot \text{sh} \chi} \quad \text{avec } \chi = \sqrt{\frac{pe^2}{a}} \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_e^*(p^*) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{p^*} \cdot \text{sh} \sqrt{p^*}} \quad \text{avec } p^* = \frac{pe^2}{a} \quad (8)$$

5. SANDWICH QUADRIPOLE

Figure 4: Sample summated to a Flash on its upper face and experimental thermogram.

We can use the quadripolar analogy to describe heat unidirectional transfer in the sample. We shall consider a cylindrical sample sandwiched between two disks without an internal source (see figure 4), initially at the same temperature. The e_1 thick disk is made of a substance having a thermal conductivity of λ_1 , its thermal capacity is c_1 , its density is ρ_1 , and the film coefficient of heat transfer from the sample to the air may be h . c_1 , λ_1 and h being assumed as constant in the range temperature measurements. On the upper and lower metallic face, heat is given up to environment by convection and by radiation. The radiation effect will be considered as included in the convection effect. It is obvious that radiative and convective heat exchange can be identified by the quadripole

according to the relation :

$$\Delta\Phi(t) = \Phi_0(t) - \Phi_e(t) = h \cdot S (T(t) - T_{ext}) \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta_0 \\ \varphi_0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ h & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_e \\ \varphi_e \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The metal disk has a thermal conductivity higher than the insulation material, this leads that the quadripolar of the disk can be expressed as [2]

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ \rho_1 c_1 e_1 p & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ C_1 p & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

because $ch c_1 \approx 1$ and $sh c_1 \approx c_1$ So between the inlet and outlet parameter, we have the relation

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta_0 \\ \varphi_0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ h & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ C_1 p & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & A \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ h & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_e \\ \varphi_e \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{eq} & B_{eq} \\ C_{eq} & A_{eq} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_e \\ \varphi_e \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The modelisation of the unidirectional heat transfer in the sandwich, with the analogical quadripolar analysis, is represented on figure

Figure 5 : quadripole of the sample and the two disks.

$$H^* = \frac{hc}{\lambda} ; p^* = p \frac{\rho_1 c_1 e_1}{\lambda} ; C^* = \frac{\rho c e}{\rho_1 c_1 e_1} ; \theta_e^* = \frac{\lambda}{Qe} \theta_e(p) \quad (13)$$

$$\theta_e^*(p^*) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{p^* C^*} \cdot sh \sqrt{p^* C^*} + 2 ch \sqrt{p^* C^*} (p^* + H^*) + \frac{sh \sqrt{p^* C^*}}{\sqrt{p^* C^*}} (p^* + H^*)^2} \quad (14)$$

5.1. Wing approximation :

If we want to consider the side exchange , we use the "wing approximation " [2]. First consider the heat balance for a differential element contained within two planes perpendicular to the sample axis at a distance x and $x + dx$ from the upper face (figure 6). There is a heat flow by conduction q_a , originating from the upper disk, and another one q_b in the direction of the opposite disk. Furthermore, an amount q_c is given by convection from the insulating material to the air . There will be a heat balance of incoming and out going heat energy

$$q_a - q_b = q_c = h m (T(x,t) - T_{ext})$$

Figure 6 : heat exchange in the sample : Wing approximation

So the heat equation is

$$\frac{\partial^2 T(x,t)}{\partial x^2} - \frac{hm}{\lambda S} T(x,t) = \frac{\partial^2 T(x,t)}{\partial x^2} - \frac{2h}{\lambda r} T(x,t) = \frac{1}{a} \frac{\partial T(x,t)}{\partial t} \quad (15)$$

where $m = 2\pi r$; $S = \pi r^2$ and $-\frac{hm}{\lambda S} T(x,t)$ is the negative term source.

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta(x,p)}{\partial x^2} = \left[\frac{p}{a} + \frac{2h}{\lambda r} \right] \theta(x,p) \quad (16)$$

It is the classical heat transfer equation in which p/a is substituted for $p/a + 2h/\lambda r$. Using the adimensionnless variable R^* , the product p^*C^* becomes $p^*C^* + 2H^*/R^*$. thus the final expression of $q^*_e(p)$ is

$$\theta_c^*(p^*) = \frac{1}{\kappa \cdot sh \kappa + 2 ch \kappa (p^* + H^*) + \frac{sh \kappa}{\kappa} (p^* + H^*)^2} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{with } \kappa = \sqrt{p^*C^* + \frac{2H^*}{R^*}}$$

We use a numerical method for Laplace Inversion [4].

6. IDENTIFICATION OF THE TRANSIENT HEAT TRANSFER:

Figure 7 : example of a Thermogram of rear face.

From the experimental thermogram, we must find the dimensionless variables H^* and t^* which will give h and

We have made a computer program which find the variables H^* and t^* It identify the rate $\frac{t_{1/3}^*}{t_{9/10}^*}$ of the measure and the rate $\frac{t_{1/3}^*}{t_{9/10}^*}$ of the theoretical curve.

From the adimensionneless variables we can have the thermal conductivity of the sample λ .

As we know that $t^* = \frac{a t}{e^2}$, one can write

$$\lambda = \frac{t_{1/3}^*}{t_{9/10}^*} \rho c e_1 \quad (18)$$

The Flash method and its identification technic have been tested on sample of polyvinyl chloride, the results were satisfactory. The measurement fluctuations were about 3% [2,3].

7. APPLICATIONS

The method, that we have presented here, permit the measure of the thermal conductivity of polymers or other low conductor materials.

The thermal conductivity depend of the conductivity of its components of the material

The measure interest is for example to have information of the rate of fibbers in the materials or the rate of pores.

When we made recycling materials all this rates have a lot of influence on the mechanics properties of the materials

When the recycling materials is made the rate of hole is not constant, that involve variable mechanic properties. With a simple conductivity control we can detect variation of its characteristics.

7.1. Measures on polyurethane foams.

Figure 8 :relationship between the conductivity and the cells sizes.

On can see that the radiative conductivity (figure 8) occurs in the global heat transfer [5] for about 30%.

We show above on the graph that the mean the thermal conductivity changes with the cell sizes. It is the thickness effect [6,7]

A gauging made, we can detect a variation of the scales of the mechanics properties if we measure the global conductivity of the sample.

7.2. Measures on recycling polymers.

We also measure the conductivity of recycling polymeric materials. These materials are compress powder. So there is some air between the small particles and the thermal conductivity of such material is relatively low.

A simple conductivity control can make appear the crushing gap.

Thickness (mm)	Conductivity (W/m.K)
4	0.24
9	0.24
11	0.24

Table 1 : conductivity for some thickness

Example of measure

We calculate on the experiment curve the rate $\frac{t_{1/3}}{t_{9/10}}$,

The experimental data give the rate R^* and H^* , so the program calculate the value of $t^{*1/3}$.

And we can have λ by the expression :

$$\lambda = \frac{t^*}{t_{1/3}} \rho c e_1$$

$$\lambda = \frac{1.24}{14.5} \cdot 8200 \cdot 420 \cdot 2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot 4 \cdot 10^{-3} = 0.24 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$$

7.3. Measures on polycarbonates.

We also measure the conductivity of polycarbonates. We made measures of the Young Module and the conductivity of the materials for several fiber rate.

The results are given on the following table.

Fiber rate (%)	Conductivity (W/m.K)	Young Module MPa
10	0.19	2400
20	0.21	4500
30	0.22	6700

Table 2 : conductivity and young Module versus fiber rate.

We see the impact of the fiber rate on the thermal properties and the connection with the Young Module

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a quick method to measure the thermal conductivity of polymers which have a conductivity lowest than 1 W/m.K , which is an adaptation of the Flash method. The modelling was made using the quadripoles and the Laplace Transform. We have determined the equivalent quadripole to the sample made up with an insulation layer and 2 metal disks which permit the amassing of heat and thermal measurement. A problem we encountered was the inversion of Laplace Transform, which we overcame by using a numerical Laplace Transform. The apparatus has been tested with classical substances, and gave total satisfactions.

The measure can be made on all materials which have a low conductivity. With a pastry cutter, we can easily make a sample and after few minutes, we can have the thermal conductivity, so some information on the characteristics of the material.

Most recycling materials have low conductivity because the compacting is not perfect and they are made with polymer which conductivity is lower than 1 W/m.K , so the conductivity is low and the measure of these last one can give information of the compression level or on the fiber rate or another process parameter.

The knowing of thermal characteristics is also useful in dynamic studies.

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